

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

Toshkent 2025

UDK:

**“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot
kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plami**

“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plamida jami 94 ta ilmiy maqola kiritilgan bo‘lib, mazkur maqolalar Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi iqtisod, siyosat, madaniyat, turizm sohalaridagi hamkorlik va imkoniyatlar, Barqaror kelajak uchun suv resurslarini boshqarishda iqlim o‘zgarishining roli, o‘rta asr Markaziy Osiyo allomalari ilmiy merosining uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishdagi ahamiyati, Turkiy davlatlarda transport, muxandislik kommunikatsiyalari, energetika, logistika, turizm sohalaridagi integratsiya jarayonlari, Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi raqamli transformatsiya, fan, ta‘lim va innovatsion rivojlanish istiqbollari kabi yo‘nalishlarni ilmiy jihatdan ochib berilishiga qaratilgan. To‘plamda o‘zbek, rus, ozarbayjon, ingliz tillarida tayyorlangan maqolalar mavjud. Ushbu konferensiya to‘plamidan transport, iqtisodiyot, falsafa, pedagogika va tarix yo‘nalishidagi tadqiqotchilar keng foydalanishi mumkin.

Mas‘ul muharrir: Ramatov Jumaniyoz Sultonovich

Muharrir: Baratov Rashit O‘sarovich

Tahrir hay‘ati:

Matkarimova J.D.	Sultanov S.S.
Salimov B.L.	Nazarova N.J.
Rajabov H.I.	Jumaniyazova N.S.
Umarova R.Sh.	Abdullayev B.B.
Baratov R.O‘.	Valiyev L.A.
Xaydarov A.	Burgutxonov S.
Jumaniyozov B.	Mamadaliyeva T.
Erniyozov U.K.	Kushakov F.A.
Abdukarimova G.B.	

“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta‘lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrda “2025-yilda xalqaro va respublika miqyosida o‘tkaziladigan ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik tadbirlar rejalarini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi 490-son buyrug‘i hamda Toshkent davlat transport universiteti rektorining 2025-yil 23-apreldagi 108-U sonli buyrug‘i asosida tashkil etildi

©Toshkent davlat transport universiteti – 2025-yil

**II SHO‘BA – BARQAROR KELAJAK UCHUN SUV RESURSLARINI
BOSHQARISHDA IQLIM O‘ZGARISHINING ROLI**

PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF GLOBAL WARMING

AZAMAT MUXTAROV

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti professori

Anotasiya: Mazkur maqolada asosiy e'tibor global isishning falsafiy tahliliga qaratilgan. Unga ko'ra denyoda kechayotgan global isishning mazmun -mohiyati, xususiyatlari tahlil qilinib, keltirib chiqadigan sabab va oqibatlari atroflicha yoritilgan. Xususan, global iqlimning barqaror taraqqiyotga, iqtisodiyot, inson sog'ligi va umuman insoniyatga tahtid ekanligiga urg'u qaratilgan holda uni bartaraf etishning falsafiy tamoyillari (ustuvorliklar va qadriyatlarni qayta ko'rib chiqish, global hamkorlik va hamjihatlik, adolat va ma'naviyat ustuvorligi, ta'lim va tarbiya uyg'unligi, daxldorlik, etika va ma'suliyat) hamda yo'nalishlari tadqiq etilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье основное внимание уделяется философскому анализу глобального потепления. Следовательно, в статье анализируются сущность, особенности глобального потепления и всесторонне освещаются причины и следствия, которые возникают. В частности, были рассмотрены философские принципы и направления по преодолению глобального изменения климата с акцентом на устойчивое развитие, экономику, здоровье человека и человечество в целом (переосмысление приоритетов и ценностей, глобальное сотрудничество и солидарность, приоритет справедливости и духовности, гармония образования и воспитания, сопричастность, этика и ответственность).

Absrtact: This article focuses on the philosophical analysis of global warming. Consequently, the article analyzes the essence and features of global warming and comprehensively highlights the causes and consequences that arise. In particular, philosophical principles and directions for overcoming global climate change were considered, with an emphasis on sustainable development, the economy, human health and humanity as a whole (rethinking priorities and values, global cooperation and solidarity, priority of justice and spirituality, harmony of education and upbringing, belonging, ethics and responsibility).

Kalit so'zlar: global isish, falsafiy tahlil, inson sog'ligi, barqaror taraqqiyot, sabab va oqibat, hamkorlik, adolat va ma'rifatlilik.

Ключевые слова: глобальное потепление, философский анализ, здоровье человека, устойчивое развитие, причина и следствие, сотрудничество, справедливость и просвещение.

Key words: global warming, philosophical analysis, human health, sustainable development, cause and effect, cooperation, justice and education.

INTRODUCTION: Global problems in the world pose a serious threat to human life. In fact, it should be noted that the emergence of such global problems is caused by the fact that man himself uses nature improperly. Global warming means an increase in the average temperature on the surface of the Earth's crust, and this process has far-reaching environmental, social and economic consequences for humanity [IPCC, 2021].

Indeed, it is worth noting that this problem also concerns Uzbekistan. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the UN General Assembly in September, noted that over the past thirty years, the air temperature in the region has increased by one and a half degrees. "This is twice the average global warming rate. As a result, almost a third of the total glacier area was lost. As long as you continue this trend, the flow of the region's two largest

rivers, the Amu Darya and the Syr Darya, may decrease by 15 percent in the next twenty years." [ogoh.uz/63378 1. 2023].

Scientific studies show that the average global temperature has increased by 1.1°C over the past hundred years, and this trend is expected to continue [NASA, 2.2023]. Methodology and literature analysis on the topic of "Philosophical interpretation of global warming", the methods of system analysis, content analysis and systematization were used as the main method. On the issue of ecology, which poses a danger to the whole of world, the head of state Sh.M.Mirziyoyev recognized the very important in his work "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity[3.2017]". The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov in his book "Uzbekistan at the dawn of the 21st century: Security threats, conditions of stability and guarantees of progress" [4.2002] specifically mentioned environmental threats. The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan defines the essence of environmental factors as a set of certain environmental conditions and elements that have a specific effect on the functioning of organisms [5.2005]. It is obvious that improving people's well-being due to the environmental crisis in the near future will show its negative consequences [6.2010]. The only way out is to switch to ecological economics or "green economics". In order to rid environmental problems of threats emanating from the world, it is necessary to emphasize that the entire world community must solve them together, with a united front[7.2023].

DISCUSSION: When looking for a solution to a problem, it is considered advisable to study the causes and consequences of the ongoing processes. In this sense, the main causes of global warming are related to human activity. In particular, greenhouse gases (carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrogen oxides (N₂O)), which have been actively released into the atmosphere since the Industrial Revolution, are one of the main factors of global warming [Lindsay & Dahlman, 2020]. As a result of the use of fossil fuels (coal, oil and gas), deforestation, agricultural and industrial activities, the proportion of gases that enhance the greenhouse effect in the atmosphere has increased dramatically.

In addition, natural processes also affect global warming to some extent. For example, changes in volcanic activity and solar radiation have affected climate in historical times. However, the rate of warming observed in the last century is attributed to the influence of human activities that contribute to unusual changes in the climate system [IPCC, 2021]. Changes in one climate system are not limited to rising temperatures. They have a number of interrelated consequences, such as rising sea levels, melting glaciers, frequent extreme weather events, and adverse impacts on biodiversity [IPCC, 2018]. It is worth noting that understanding global warming is important not only from the point of view of natural sciences, but also from a philosophical point of view. This problem requires a revision of the relationship between man and nature, and an awareness of humanity's moral responsibility for its actions [Gardiner, 2011].

RESULT: Naturally, global warming is causing fundamental changes in the ecosystems of the Earth's Crust. An increase in atmospheric temperature causes an imbalance in the natural environment, serious changes in the animal and plant world [IPCC, 2019]. First, there is a rapid melting of ice sheets in the glaciers of the Arctic and Antarctic. For example, the glaciers of Greenland and Antarctica are losing billions of tons of ice every year [NASA, 2022]. This process leads to sea level rise, which increases the risk of flooding in coastal areas. The second aspect is the reduction of biodiversity due to climate change. Due to warming, many species are losing their living space or are forced to move. For example, areas such as tropical forests and coral reefs have been severely affected by global warming [WWF, 2020].

The process of coral bleaching occurring on coral reefs directly depends on the warming of ocean water. Global warming is also seriously affecting agriculture. Rising temperatures, changes in precipitation, and extreme climatic events (mild droughts or heavy rains) lead to lower crop yields [FAO, 2021]. This will exacerbate the problem of food safety and increase the risk of malnutrition among infants and adults in some regions.

Environmental impacts have a strong influence not only on the environment, but also on human society. Natural disasters (torrential rains, forest fires, droughts) not only cause economic damage, but also pose a serious threat to human health and public safety [WHO, 2021].

Indeed, the environmental consequences of global warming indicate that the balance between *human activity and the natural environment* is seriously disrupted. This makes, from a philosophical point of view, man's responsibility to nature and the obligation to protect it a more pressing issue [Jamieson, 2010]. Social and economic consequences of global warming. Global warming has a negative impact not only on the natural environment, but also on human society and its economic systems. Rising temperatures, changing climatic conditions, and frequent natural disasters have a direct impact on people's lives (Stern, 2007). If we consider the problem from a social point of view, then global warming leads to the phenomenon of population migration — "climate migrants". According to the United Nations [UNHCR, 2021], millions of people are forced to leave their homes every year as a result of drought, floods or reduced land productivity. This leads to new social crises, competition for resources, and sometimes political instability. In particular, in economic terms, global warming will lead to huge financial losses. For example, losses due to natural disasters, deteriorating infrastructure, declining agricultural productivity, and increased health care costs have a serious impact on the economies of many countries [OECD, 1.2021]. In the United States alone, annual economic losses from natural disasters related to climate change are expected to exceed \$120 billion [EPA, 2. 2022].

Considering today's reality, it is worth noting that due to the warming in the agricultural sector, the yield of products is decreasing. As a result of rising temperatures and water shortages, yields of cereals, rice, and other staple foods may decrease [Lobell et al., 3.2011]. This further exacerbates the problem of food security. Naturally, the healthcare sector is also suffering from global warming. As temperatures rise, the number of diseases increases, including the number of heart attacks and strokes associated with abnormal heat [WHO, 4.2021].

It is also noted that infectious diseases such as malaria and dengue are spreading to new geographical areas. Global warming also requires a review of the situation in the energy sector. Due to the increase in the number of iscars, the demand for air cooling systems is increasing, which dramatically increases electricity consumption and at the same time creates the need to use new renewable sources [IEA, 5.2022].

Overall, global warming is exacerbating social problems, threatening economic stability, and causing significant changes in all aspects of human life. Consequently, from a philosophical point of view, global warming also requires revision in the context of issues of human responsibility, equality and justice [Gardiner, December 6, 2011]. Global warming and philosophical analysis. The problem of global warming is not only an environmental or economic problem, but also has a deep philosophical content. This issue requires a review of the relationship between man and nature, and a philosophical understanding of human responsibility, justice, and duty to future generations [Gardiner, December 7, 2011].

First of all, the philosophy of responsibility plays an important role in solving the problem of global warming. The rapid and disproportionate consumption of natural resources by the current generation for economic development threatens the existence of future generations

[Jonas, 8. 1984]. According to the theory of Hans Jonas "the imperative of responsibility", a person is obliged to think deeply about the consequences of his actions in relation to nature and the future.

Secondly, global warming is also analyzed from the point of view of *spiritual and moral justice*. While climate change is largely caused by developed countries, poorer and developing countries are feeling its terrible effects [Shue, 9.2014]. This further exposes the problem of global inequality. From a philosophical point of view, this situation is assessed as an "incorrect uneven distribution of conditions" (distributive injustice).

The third aspect is the philosophy of *harmony between man and nature*. In traditional Western thought, nature has often been viewed as a useful resource for humans [White, 10.1967]. But environmental crises, in particular global warming, have shown that nature is not just an object of consumption, but a necessary and equal participant in human life. The idea of ecocentrism requires the formation of a new, stable relationship between man and nature [Naess, 11.1973].

The fourth philosophical point of view is the *issue of the rights of future generations*. The duty of the current generation is to protect the living conditions and opportunities of people who will live in the future [Rolls, 12/1999]. In this context, denying climate change or failing to take adequate measures can be regarded as a moral and legal flaw.

The fifth aspect is the philosophy of disaster. It is suggested that the problem of global warming may in some cases reach an irreversible point [Lenton et al., 13.2008]. If the climate systems undergo catastrophic changes, then humanity itself can lead to an uncontrollable catastrophe. This requires a rethinking of philosophical territorial and universal concepts of responsibility. In general, the problem of global warming makes us rethink the role of man in nature, moral responsibility and universal justice. Philosophical analysis shows that the problem of global warming should be solved not only by practical measures, but also by reformatting universal values and principles. We see a vivid example of this in the works of "Avesto", A.Navoi, U.Hayam and Z.M. Bobur.

CONCLUSION: It is certain that an effective fight against global warming today requires not only technical or political measures, but also philosophical approaches. To solve this problem, it is necessary to radically change human thinking, values and attitudes [Jamison, 14.2014].

The first area is the *principles of ethics and responsibility*. On the issue of global warming, there is a moral responsibility of every person, society and the state. As Hans Jonas notes, any technological activity is necessarily carried out taking into account the interests of future generations [Jonas, 14. 1984]. Viewed from this perspective, all decisions and actions should be based on the ethical standards of the future.

The second direction is *the principles of justice and equality*. In the global fight against climate change, all countries must share their responsibilities fairly [Keiney, December 15, 2010]. Each state will have certain responsibilities depending on its history, level of economic development and contribution to carbon emissions. This is justified by the theory of "viewing opportunities and fair distribution of contributions."

The third direction is the *idea of living in harmony with nature*. Instead of the traditional relationship between man and natural resources, new relationships based on the principles of cooperation and mutual respect between man and nature should be formed [Leopold, December 16, 1949]. Aldo Leopold's theory of "ethics of the earth" suggests considering nature as a moral partner, and not just as a source of profit.

The fourth direction is *the revision of priorities and values*. Combating global warming is achieved not only through technological inventions or legislation; it requires changing people's lifestyles, consumer culture, and values [Latour, 17.2017]. It is necessary to abandon the ideas of material well-being and unlimited growth and strive for a new social balance based on the principles of stability and moderation.

The fifth direction is *cooperation and global harmony*. Since global warming is a problem that knows no borders, its solution also requires solidarity and cooperation at the global level [Hume, 18.2009]. It is necessary to create an effective atmosphere of dialogue and cooperation between all countries, organizations and individuals in order to solve the climate problem as a universal responsibility. At the same time, the role of education and enlightenment also plays an incomparable role. It is necessary to educate the new generation *in the spirit of environmental awareness and responsibility*, to form a systematic approach to global problems based on the harmony of science and philosophy [O'Brien, 19.2012].

In general, the fight against global warming requires not only technical and political measures, but also philosophical analysis, a radical change in human consciousness and values. The responsibility and active participation of each individual in this process is crucial.

REFERENCES:

1. BMT Bosh Assambleyasi Markaziy Osiyodagi ekologik muammolarga qarshi kurash bo'yicha rezolyusiyani qabul qildi. <https://ogoh.uz/63378/>
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik-har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo'lishi kerak. - T.: O'zbekiston, 2017, 19-b.
3. Karimov I.A. O'zbekiston XXI asr bo'sag'asida: xavfsizlikka tahdid, barqarorlik shartlari va taraqqiyot kafolatlari. -T.: Moliya.2002. 11-14-bb.
4. O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasi. -T.: Davlat ilmiy.2005. 164b.
5. UNEP, 2011, Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication, (predvaritelniy variant), <http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy>
6. Плеханов С.И. Солнце – это жизнь, а не батарейка. Химия и жизнь, №8 стр. 2012, с.2-5
7. Саней, С. (2010).
7. Climate change, human rights, and moral thresholds. In S. Caney & A. P. Dobson (Eds.), *Human rights and climate change* (pp. 69-86).
8. Cambridge University Press. 8.EPA. (2022). *Climate change impacts in the United States*. Environmental Protection Agency.
9. FAO. (2021). *The state of food security and nutrition in the world 2021*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
10. Gardiner, S. M. (2011). *A perfect moral storm: The ethical tragedy of climate change*. Oxford University Press.
11. Hulme, M. (2009). *Why we disagree about climate change: Understanding controversy, inaction and opportunity*. Cambridge University Press.
12. IEA. (2022). *World energy outlook 2022*. International Energy Agency.
13. IPCC. (2018). *Global warming of 1.5°C: An IPCC special report*. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>
14. IPCC. (2019). *Climate change and land: An IPCC special report*. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/srcl/>
15. IPCC. (2021). *Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report*. Cambridge University Press.
16. Jamieson, D. (2010). *Climate change and global environmental justice*. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 16(3), 431-445.
17. Jamieson, D. (2014). *Reason in a dark time: Why the struggle against climate change failed — and what it means for our future*. Oxford University Press

18. Jonas, H. (1984). *The imperative of responsibility: In search of an ethics for the technological age*. University of Chicago Press.
19. Latour, B. (2017). *Facing Gaia: Eight lectures on the new climatic regime*. Polity Press.